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DMRT1 epigenetic control through Dlx5.

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We identified *DMRT1* interaction partners by ectopic expression of DMRT1 in a human primordial germ-like stem cell culture system coupled with measurement of total transcription by next generation RNA-sequencing. DMRT1 interacted with the imprinting axis involving Xist-Dlx-Olig activation-repression through Dlx5. A second key transcriptional partner of DMRT1 in epigenetic reprogramming was Zic5.

Citations

- 1.